

STUDY ON STRUCTURE AND GROWTH OF BANKING INDUSTRY IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

Financial development is a functioning and consistent process and banks are the principal players of monetary advancement of a nation. The productive working of the managing an account division in India assumes conclusive job in the general development of the financial system in the nation. The motivation behind the present part is to bless with a review of Indian saving money segment execution after the execution of deregulatory measures amid 1993-94. The procedure of financial deregulation include changes in the loan costs, credit rates, store rates, dimension of rivalry, basic changes, association of predominant innovation, proprietorship design, facilitating of arrangements, and so forth in India. These progressions prompted the advancement of upgraded and enhanced administrations given by financial middle people, in this way, go about as a vital part for the general development and development.

Key words: Investment, Deposits, NPA, Credit-Deposits, Investment-Deposits.

1. INTRODUCTION

The worldwide emergency has drawn fear about the job and the operational execution of the financial sector in various economies of the world. It has raised concern with respect to the pretended by the financial sector for the economic development of nations. Because of log jam in worldwide economic advancement, the policymakers have gone up against with difficulties that have made specialists to manage financial and fiscal arrangements in a clashing circumstance. It has been closed from the outcomes that Indian saving money sector does not rank high on the general score of financial development file. The rate offer of branches in provincial fragments delineates decay and with the entry of change process, while, increment in the store and credit assembly if there should be an occurrence of banks in metropolitan territories in India has been taken note. Nonetheless, the procedure of deregulation and changed approaches has made the development for private and outside sector banks than the nationalized banks and SBI gathering. Likewise, the part uncovered that the effect of financial emergency regarding the most recent couple of years has made the direction course back to the nationalized banks and SBI gather as far as advances, speculation and stores than private and FSBs. The investigation by Acharya and Kulkarni (2011) affirms this did not occur because of the strength of state claimed banks than the PSBs and FSB yet because of unequivocal and understood government support of open sector banks in India. There has additionally been drop in the level of parts of nationalized bank and SBI bunch amid 2009-10 with a peripheral recuperation in 2010-11. Strikingly, the managing an account sector execution is by all accounts basically influenced by the financial emergency regarding stores, advances and speculations. It has been recommended that there has been critical upgrades in the execution of the Indian keeping money sector after post-change period, in spite of the fact that the level of enhancements fluctuate macross diverse markers. The most critical commitment has been seen if there should arise an occurrence of profits on resources and profits for value over the period of time. It has been mirrored that banks confronting the outcomes of strict standards and controls started by RBI, time to time, are as yet leading their activities profitability. Another pointer found to have critical commitment is C-D proportion. This proportion has appeared after gradual development. The aftereffects of these pointers are authenticated with the investigations of What's more, it has been seen that the proportion of wage bill to add up to costs have declined altogether, accordingly, mirroring the effect of strengthening competitive weights. At long last, it very well may be finished up from the above

dialog that saving money sector in India has given blended outcome after the inception of changes set out by RBI and legislature of India. It has been affirmed that managing an account sector in India is developing at a decent pace and in a sound way with exemption to most recent couple of years. It has been, further, uncovered that booked business banks in India have reacted emphatically in the field of profitability, profitability, resources quality, i.e., decrease of NPAs, improving the job of market powers, standards of prudential controls of bookkeeping, salary acknowledgment, provisioning and presentation, presentation of CAMEL supervisory rating system and nonstop upgradation of innovation to give better and proficient administrations to the clients. In any case, it has been seen that the execution of business banks in India amid 2011-12 was adapted by the log jam in residential economy combined with higher loan costs in condition however Indian banks stayed all around promoted. financial crisis over the last few years has made the trajectory direction back to the nationalized banks and SBI group in terms of advances, investment and deposits than private and FSBs. The study by confirms that this did not happen due to the resilience of state owned banks than the PSBs and FSB but due to explicit and implicit government backing of public sector banks in India. There has also been drop in the percentage of branches of nationalized bank and SBI group during 2009-10 with a marginal recovery in 2010-11. Interestingly, the banking sector performance seems to be virtually affected by the financial crisis in terms of deposits, advances and investments. It has been suggested that there has been significant improvements in the performance of the Indian banking sector after post-reform period, although the degree of improvements vary across different indicators. The most significant contribution has been observed in case of returns on assets and returns on equity over the period of time. It has been reflected that banks facing the consequences of strict norms and regulations initiated by RBI, time to time, are still conducting their operations profitability. Another indicator found to have significant contribution is C-D ratio. This ratio has shown improvements after slow and steady growth

2.COMPARISONS OF ECONOMIES IN FINANCIAL DEVELOPMENT INDEX.

The execution, long haul development, welfare and development of an economy, is identified with its level of financial development. Higher the level of financial development, more extensive will be the financial administrations. The European National Bank, amid 2009 by building up a composite list utilizing twenty-one pointers, positioned India twenty-second among thirty nations. The investigation reasoned that India performed better in the financial market and require enhancements in the business condition An endeavor made by recommended significance of created financial market for the long-run

monetary development. The examination foreseen rules for future development of the financial market in India. For an exhaustive disregard at the financial development of economies, World Monetary Discussion introduced the Financial Development Report utilizing the scale extending from 1-7, where 1 being the slightest and 7 being the most favorable to the financial development. These reports look for after explicit limitations on account of radical change in condition and some intriguing states of economies. It in like manner gives an expansive structure of the data to the extent record speaking to the development of financial system. The financial development list gives an understanding around three noteworthy markers explicitly factors, approaches and foundations; financial intermediation and financial access. These files are additionally portioned into seven pointers i.e., institutional condition, business condition, financial solidness, bank elements, non-bank substances, financial markets and financial access (Financial Development Report, World Economic The preservationist approach has been received for doling out the loads to the individual factors. Every one of the pointers have been relegated the heaviness of 14.29 percent which is further subject to various parameters related with these seven markers (see Financial Development Report, World Economic Gathering, 2013 for subtleties). It has been demonstrated that regarding by and large positioning on the financial development record, India has tumbled down to 40th position amid the year 2013 (allude Table 4.1). The decrease saw amid the year 2013 was because of the European Emergency and ascend in Oil costs which has influenced every one of the economies of the world (Financial Development Report, World Economic Discussion, 2013).

TABLE 2.1: RANK WISE COMPARISONS OF ECONOMIES IN FINANCIAL DEVELOPMENT INDEX.

Country	Rank			Score (1-7)		
	2013	2012	2011	2013	2012	2011
Hong Kong	1	1	3	5.31	5.16	5.04
United States	2	2	1	5.27	5.15	5.12
United Kingdom	3	3	2	5.21	5.00	5.06

Singapore	4	4	4	5.10	4.97	5.03
Australia	5	5	5	5.01	4.93	5.01
Canada	6	6	6	5.00	4.86	4.98
Japan	7	8	9	4.90	4.71	4.67
Switzerland	8	9	8	4.78	4.63	4.71
Netherlands	9	7	7	4.73	4.71	4.73
Sweden	10	11	12	4.71	4.51	4.60
China	23	19	22	4.00	4.12	4.03
Federation	39	39	40	3.30	3.18	3.21
India	40	36	37	3.29	3.29	3.24
Indonesia	50	51	51	2.95	2.85	2.90
Source: Financial Development Report, World Economic Forum, 2013						

The relative examination over the period of three years have appeared out of sixty-four nations, India, as creating country, is performing great on the seven point scale. Nonetheless, it has been seen that India does not rank high on its general score, however, it is moderately very much set in non keeping money financial administrations (ninth) and financial market (twenty-eighth) (allude Figure 2.1)

FIGURE 2.1: RANK OF INDICATORS ON FINANCIAL DEVELOPMENT INDEX OF INDIA FOR 2013

Source: Financial Development Report, World Economic Forum, 2013

Economies. Hence, it becomes a topic of concern to analyze the structure, growth and development of Indian banking sector over the past two decades. The present chapter has focused on various indicators to highlight the position of banking sector in India. The present chapter of the study is divided into two sections. The first section highlights descriptive measures of performance using various financial indicators and accounting ratios. The discussions will reveal the importance of the sound financial sector, as the necessary condition for progress and development of an economy. In addition, the section has discussed technological developments introduced by the banking sector in India. The section second is related with the measurement of performance of the banking sector in India using CAMEL approach.

3. DESCRIPTIVE MEASURES OF PERFORMANCE

The banking sector in India has registered changes in framework, regulations, organizational structures and scope of business activities. It has witnessed rapid growth during the deregulation of economy.

These initiatives have transformed the entire structure of the banking sector in India and brought changes in the momentum of operation in banks. As more than two decades since the initiation of deregulation process introduced into the India banking sector. The present study tried to capture the impact of these reforms on the performance scheduled commercial banks (SCBs) over the period of time. The number of commercial banks in India has decreased from 284 during Further, the number of SCBs reduced from 289 to 151 (including 82 RRBs) and non-scheduled commercial banks from 16 to 4 over the period of time.

It has been depicted in the Table 3.1 that the flow of credit provided to the priority section (agriculture and small scale industries) in India shows consistency. There has been growth observed in the advances provided to priority sector from ` 692.0 crore during

The common approach to determine the performance of the banking sector, wherein the position of bank can be judged, is in terms of certain key indicators and their ratios. However, all these indicators are interlinked with each other. The deposit and credit mobilization determines the core of banking business. Similarly, the investment of bank in terms of government and non-government securities hypothesized the source of funds borrowed from domestic or international market. Further, the competency of banks can be determined in terms of profitability ratios like returns on asset, returns on equity, wage bill to total expenses and technological advancements over the period of time across different banks.

He comparative position for the branch distribution reveals that the rural branches of SCBs in India have decreased from 55.9 per cent to 37.17 per cent over the period of time with slight recovery during terminal years of the study. This fall in rural branch network was due to continuous focus on up gradation in technology by banking sector and a progressive reduction in the physical branches of the banks. Moreover, during 1998, RBI allowed banks to shut those branches that were found to face losses for three consecutive years (Reserve Bank of India, On the contrary, slight improvements have been observed in the percentage of semi-urban, urban and metropolitan areas during the post-deregulation period. The branches in semi-urban, urban and metropolitan have increased from 19.0 per cent to 26.71 per cent, 14.20 per cent to 18.87 .

Table 3.1: Percentage Distribution Of Branches, Deposits And Credit Of Scheduled Commercial Banks

Year	NO CB	SC Bs	PS/TA	Branches				Deposits				Credit			
				Rural	Semi-Urban	Urban	Metropolitan	Rural	Semi-Urban	Urban	Metropolitan	Rural	Semi-Urban	Urban	Metropolitan
1994-95	284	281	692.00	55.90	19.00	14.20	10.10	15.00	18.80	23.20	42.40	14.00	14.00	20.40	51.60
1995-96	284	281	692.00	52.92	21.39	14.22	11.47	15.20	19.50	22.90	42.40	11.90	13.50	18.60	56.00
1996-97	293	291	808.31	52.35	21.52	14.42	11.72	13.70	18.80	22.20	45.30	11.40	13.10	17.70	57.80

199																
7-				51.	21.6			14.	19.5			11.	13.1	17.6		
98	299	297	938.00	79	6	14.70	11.85	40	0	22.40	43.70	40	0	0	57.90	
199																
8-			1089.0	51.	21.7			14.	19.6			11.	12.8	17.6		
99	300	299	0	20	7	14.94	12.09	70	0	22.50	43.20	40	0	0	58.20	
199																
9-			1263.0	50.	21.8			14.	19.4			11.	12.7	17.8		
00	303	302	0	60	2	15.24	12.34	50	0	22.60	43.50	00	0	0	58.50	
200																
0-			1557.7	50.	22.0			14.	19.5			10.	12.2	17.2		
01	297	297	0	04	3	15.37	12.56	70	0	22.90	42.90	60	0	0	60.00	
200																
1-			1822.5	49.	22.1			14.	19.7			10.	11.5	17.4		
02	301	296	0	40	4	15.61	12.84	70	0	23.00	42.60	20	0	0	61.00	
200																
2-			2056.0	48.	22.2			14.	19.6			10.	11.2	16.5		
03	298	294	0	92	8	15.83	12.97	70	0	22.90	42.80	20	0	0	62.10	

200															
3-			2546.4	48.	22.3			14.	19.1			10.	11.3	16.4	
04	294	289	0	55	3	16.07	13.05	20	0	22.80	43.90	20	0	0	62.10
200															
4-			3113.3	47.	22.4			13.	18.9			9.7	11.4	17.1	
05	291	286	0	81	6	16.37	13.36	80	0	22.80	44.50	0	0	0	61.90
200															
5-			4007.7	46.	22.5			12.	17.7			9.5	11.3	16.4	
06	288	284	0	93	3	16.82	13.71	90	0	21.90	47.50	0	0	0	62.70
200															
6-			5467.7	43.	22.5			12.	16.9			8.3	10.0	16.2	
07	222	218	0	22	5	17.43	16.80	20	0	21.50	49.40	0	0	0	65.40
200															
7-			7037.5	42.	22.8			10.	14.5			7.9		16.3	
08	183	179	0	00	7	18.03	17.10	80	0	20.60	54.10	0	9.70	0	66.10
200															
8-			8247.7	40.	23.3			9.7	13.8			7.6		15.9	
09	175	171	0	50	3	18.71	17.46	0	0	20.50	56.00	0	9.50	0	67.10

200															
9-			9674.13	9.23	8			9.3	13.2			7.3		16.1	
10	170	166	0	37	0	19.07	17.77	0	0	20.20	57.20	0	9.30	0	67.30
201															
0-			11384.38	12.24	3			9.3	13.5			7.5		16.7	
11	169	165	00	12	5	19.55	17.98	0	0	21.00	56.20	0	9.60	0	66.30
201															
1-			13373.37	12.25	3			9.2	13.5			7.3		16.8	
12	169	165	30	30	4	19.38	17.98	0	0	20.70	56.60	0	9.40	0	66.60
201															
2-			14713.36	12.26	2			9.2	13.3			7.5		16.8	
13	173	169	30	92	0	19.18	17.71	0	0	20.60	56.90	0	9.45	3	66.22
201															
3-			16952.37	12.26	7			9.2	13.3			8.3	10.1	16.4	
14	155	151	67	17	1	18.87	17.23	2	5	20.65	56.78	0	0	3	65.20

Source: Compiled From Various Report on Trend and Progress of Banking in India

Note: NOCB= number of commercial banks; SCBs= Scheduled Commercial Banks; PS/TA = ratio of priority sector advances to total advances

Table 3.2: ownership-wise percentage distribution of branches, deposits and credit

Year	Branches				Deposits				Credit			
	Nationalized Banks	SBI and Associates	Foreign Banks	Private Banks	Nationalized Banks	SBI and Associates	Foreign Banks	Private Banks	Nationalized Banks	SBI and Associates	Foreign Banks	Private Banks
1994-95	49.70	20.20	0.20	6.60	57.30	29.20	7.50	5.50	52.70	32.50	6.50	5.40
1995-96	49.90	20.30	0.20	6.60	53.40	29.20	7.60	6.90	53.40	29.20	7.60	6.90
1996-97	49.90	20.20	0.30	6.80	51.10	29.10	9.00	7.90	51.10	29.10	9.00	7.90

199												
7-												
98	49.90	20.20	0.30	7.10	48.90	29.20	9.30	9.50	48.90	29.20	9.30	9.50
199												
8-								10.6				10.6
99	50.00	20.10	0.30	7.40	48.70	28.60	9.00	0	48.70	28.60	9.00	0
199												
9-								11.5				11.5
00	50.10	20.00	0.30	7.60	49.20	28.10	8.20	0	49.20	28.10	8.20	0
200												
0-								12.4				12.4
01	50.10	20.10	0.30	7.70	48.70	27.60	8.40	0	48.70	27.60	8.40	0
200												
1-								13.2				13.2
02	50.10	20.10	0.30	7.80	48.60	26.80	8.40	0	48.60	26.80	8.40	0
200												
2-								17.5				17.5
03	49.80	20.10	0.30	8.20	47.30	25.00	7.30	0	47.30	25.00	7.30	0

200												
3-								19.0				19.0
04	49.90	20.10	0.30	8.10	46.80	24.10	7.10	0	46.80	24.10	7.10	0
200												
4-								19.8				19.8
05	49.90	20.00	0.30	8.50	46.40	23.70	7.20	0	46.40	23.70	7.20	0
200												
5-								19.7				19.7
06	49.80	19.80	0.30	9.10	47.80	23.10	6.60	0	47.80	23.10	6.60	0
200												
6-								20.0				20.0
07	49.80	19.80	0.30	9.40	47.90	23.10	6.60	0	47.90	23.10	6.60	0
200												
7-								20.6				20.0
08	48.05	19.67	0.37	9.95	48.50	22.20	5.60	0	47.60	23.00	6.90	0
200												
8-				10.6				20.2				19.7
09	49.84	20.12	0.35	9	48.10	23.20	5.50	0	48.80	22.10	6.70	0

2009-10	49.42	20.38	0.36	6	11.1	49.40	22.10	5.20	0	18.2	50.50	23.10	5.90	0	18.2
2010-11	49.34	20.62	0.35	5	11.8	51.90	22.30	5.00	0	17.7	52.00	23.10	4.90	0	17.5
2011-12	49.37	20.25	0.34	2	12.8	53.20	21.40	4.40	0	18.0	53.00	21.90	4.90	0	17.8
2012-13	49.93	19.55	0.32	0	13.7	55.73	21.70	4.50	0	18.1	52.40	22.80	5.00	0	18.5
2013-14	49.69	19.40	0.31	1	14.6	55.56	21.78	4.29	8	18.2	52.61	23.45	5.50	4	19.4

Source: Compiled From Various Report on Trend and Progress of Banking in India

Development.

Figure 3.1 : Percentage Share For Investments (Annual Growth Rate)

Source: Compiled From Various Report on Trend and Progress of Banking in India

Figure 3.2: Type-Wise Distribution of Deposits (Annual Growth Rate)

Source: Compiled From Various Report on Trend and Progress of Banking in India

Note: AD = Aggregate Deposits; DD = Demand Deposits; TD = Time Deposits

Figure 3.3 : NPAs Distribution over Advances and Total Assets (Annual Growth Rate)

Source: Compiled From Various Report on Trend and Progress of Banking in India

The spurt of non-performing resources (NPAs) could likewise be embraced to the lacking examination and observing of credit proposition in the household economy. To have further knowledge of NPAs, the present examination consider the example pursued by NPAs over gross advances and aggregate resources amid last one and half decades. The calculation of NPAs gives insight concerning the correct portion of assets by the banks in India to the diverse sectors of economy. It has been analysed from Figure 3.3 that NPA over the period of time has indicated consistent decay. Along these lines, an impressive advancement in the recuperation of NPAs and at a similar period of time, increment in the gross advances and advances prompted the decrease in this proportion. Further, the development of Benefit Remaking Organization Constrained (ARCIL) likewise helped a great deal in the recuperation of

levy. To abridge, the NPAs as a rate to add up to resources has delineated extreme decrease since 2001-02 and this might be because of the enhancements in the credit examination process, upturn of business cycle, new activities of NPAs like declaration and new acknowledgment for NPAs from 180 to 90 days. In any case, there is additionally a need to keep check over the proportion in light of upward movement towards the higher level during the last few years.

4.INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT IN BANKS

Throughout the years, RBI and other financial offices in India have laid uncommon accentuation on the innovation up gradation in everyday activities of banks in India. To get by without innovation in managing an account system at present period is existence without water. The implantation of innovation in keeping money sector had made managing an account sector proficient as well as has helped the progressing procedure of financial incorporation. In the ongoing years, banks have expanded the quantity of on location (71690) and off-site (69826) ATMs in different areas and have likewise begun giving managing an account offices through the cell phones of the clients, accordingly, attempting to convey their best to the clients and effort the remote territories in India (Write about Pattern and Advancement of Keeping money in India, 2012-13).

Table 4.1: Transactions through Retail Electronic Payment Methods

	2005-06	2006-07	2007-08	2008-09	2009-10	2010-11	2011-12	2012-13	2013-14
Volume (in thousands)									
ECS Credit	44216	69019	78365	88394	98100	117000	122000	122180	152540
ECS debit	35958	75202	127120	160055	149300	157000	165000	176530	192910

EFT-NEFT	3067	4776	13315	66340	132340	226110	281000	394130	661010
Credit Card	156086	169536	228203	259561	230550	265000	320000	399130	512030
Debit Card	45686	60177	88306	127654	182000	237000	328000	599921	670710
Value in crore									
ECS Credit	32324	83273	782222	97487	117613	181686	183800	177128	249219
ECS debit	12986	25441	48937	66976	69524	73646	83400	108310	126796
EFT-NEFT	61288	77446	140326	251956	409507	939149	1790350	2902242	4378552
Credit Card	33886	41361	57984	65356	58890	75500	96600	1863736	155672
Debit Card	5897	8172	12521	18547	28624	38700	53400	1739344	2060286

Source: Compiled From Various Report on Trend and Progress of Banking in India

Anyway with the selection of computerization and center keeping money arrangement system, banks are presently concentrating more on client relationship the executives and attempting to enhance their inside administration data system. The aggregate number of ATMs for planned business banks over the period of time has expanded from 27,000 of every 2007 to over 1.6 lakh the nation over in 2013-14. Therefore, in Indian market, money is for the most part utilized for the retail advances however the utilization of checks, charge cards, Visas and other installment instrument are likewise observed to be utilized at expanding rate. The volume and estimation of exchanges at present with the utilization of cards are dramatically increased in 2004-05. Thus, sharp increment in electronic store exchange (EFT) and other related electronic exchanges have been taken note. The hidden method of reasoning for the equivalent is that clients are given less expensive installment system and quicker exchange process than the paper based instruments.

What's more, the Genuine Occasions Net Settlement (RTGS) was operationalized amid the year 2004-05 for the exchange of huge measure of assets at quicker rate. From that point forward, its significance has expanded step by step. Thinking about the enormous development in the RTGS system, the specialized warning gathering of RBI evaluated the system and suggested the plan of New Age Genuine Occasions Net Settlement (NG-RTGS) to give all the more brisk and advance exchange checking and control system to expand the volume of exchanges through the RTGS system (Investigate Pattern and Advancement of Keeping money in India, 2012-13). The installment systems like electronic clearing system (both charge and credit), country electronic reserve exchange and card based systems are getting to be prominent as delineated through the expansion in the volume and estimation of exchanges (allude Table 4.4). Further, the development incline in a wide range of systems particularly ECS (credit) and ECS (charge) has made critical increment because of the immediate acknowledge, for example, compensation, annuity installments and direct charge like accumulation of bills, protection premium, compared regularly scheduled payments for advances, shopping, and so on.

5.ACCOUNTING MEASURES FOR PERFORMANCE

There has been a gradual change in the technological and operational environment in the banking sector in India after 1990s. There has been exposure to the competitive environment with the presence of foreign ownerships. The radical changes in the capital structure of banks have lead towards

diversification of business activities by the banks. All these changes have made the way for banks to make their operations efficient. Although, banks generate multiple products/services unlike firms thus the performance of banks cannot be analyzed by using usual yardsticks. Therefore, specifically two types of measures have been used to measure the performance of the banks i.e., accounting measures and economic measures. The present sub section deals with accounting measures as a tool to measure the performance of the banks over the period of time. Accounting measures refer to various financial ratios used to measure the performance of a banking unit. The present study tries to analyse performance of banks over the period of time by using financial ratios like Credit-Deposits (C-D) ratios, Investment-Deposits (I-D) ratios, ratio of Wage bill to total expenses, profitability indicators i.e. Return on Assets (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE) and Ratio of Operating Profit to total assets.

Figure 5.1 . Ratio-Wise Analysis for Credit-Deposits, Investment-Deposits and Wage Bills to Total Expenses

Source: Compiled From Various Report on Trend and Progress of Banking in India

These proportions give an understanding about the creation of aggregate business of Planned Business Banks in India. It is likewise concurred that the intermediation of assets from savers to the speculators is the most fundamental commitment of managing an account sector to the generally speaking economic development. Figure 4.5 portrays that C-D proportion has advanced over the period of time. This proportion fundamentally indicates payment of bank stores by method for advances and advances to the

clients. As affirmed by the Figure 4.5, the proportion gives off an impression of being more than 50.0 percent, while, quickening has been seen after 2008-09. Then again, the opposite pattern has been knowledgeable about instance of I-D proportion. Be that as it may, the declining pattern of stores and their constituents' along with growing worries towards NPAs in the course of the most recent couple of years can be considered as the matter of worry for the managing an account sector, in this manner, driving an effect on the I-D proportion.

Figure 5.2.: Profitability Measures of SCBs in India

source: Authors elaborations'

6.CONCLUSION

The results of these indicators are corroborated with the studies of Bhatia (1978); Reserve Bank of India In addition to this, it has been observed that the ratio of wage bill to total expenses have declined significantly, thereby, reflecting the impact of intensifying competitive pressures. Finally, it can be concluded from the above discussion that banking sector in India has provided mixed result after the initiation of reforms embarked by RBI and government of India. It has been confirmed that banking sector in India is growing at a good pace and in a healthy manner with exception to last few years. It has been, further, revealed that scheduled commercial banks in India have responded positively in the field of profitability, productivity, assets quality, i.e., reduction of NPAs, enhancing the role of market forces ,norms of prudential regulations of accounting, income recognition, provisioning and exposure, However, it has been observed that the performance of commercial banks in India during 2011-12 was conditioned by the slowdown in domestic economy coupled with higher interest

rates in environment though Indian banks remained well capitalized.

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